

WHAT ARE THEY BUYING IN PRIVATE TUITION? MICRO-LEVEL PERSPECTIVE ON THE PRACTICE OF PRIVATE TUITION BY GRADE 9 STUDENTS IN KALE TOWNSHIP, MYANMAR

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Abstract:

Private tuition is the practice of academic teaching and learning from outside of the school with a fee but a few of studies acknowledged what private tuition provides to the receivers beyond the teaching of academic subjects. This study explored the intensity and nature of private tuition through 1119 Grade 9 students' survey reports and 18 interviewees' responses. The study revealed the common practice of private tuition in Myanmar and 69.5% of the participants are in private boarding tuition. Moreover, it concluded that students get supportive services for learning in private tuition in addition to academic teachings.

Keywords: private tuition, private tutoring, shadow education, Myanmar, learning environment, high school

1. Introduction

Private tuition or private tutoring is an educational service from outside of the common school practiced by students. The term refers to the teaching and learning of school curricula from outside of the school hours with a fee. The phenomenon was first common in East Asian countries such as Sri Lanka (Bray & Lykins, 2012), Japan (Stevenson & Baker, 1992), South Korea (Lee, Lee, & Jang, 2010). However, the international development of the phenomenon is significant in many studies such as: in Africa countries (Paviot, Heinsohn, & Korkman, 2008), in eastern European countries

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and central Asian countries (Silova, 2010), in Asian countries (Bray, M., & Kwo, 2014; Bray & Lykins, 2012), and in Latin America countries and others (Bray, Kwo, & Jokić, 2015). Although the private tuition, sometimes, included the teaching of extracurricular activities such as music, sport, and art, current research explicitly refers to the purchase of core school subject teaching from outside of the school.

Generally, researchers agreed on the intention of receiving private tuition as to get something that home or/and the school did not provide sufficiently to students. Many studies hypothesized students intense to receive private tuition in order to get academic skills. However, it was inconclusive for whether or not private tuition can benefit students' academic performance. Some studies asserted the positive relationship between private tuition and students' academic achievement (Gibson, 1992; Dang & Rogers, 2008; Cayubit et al., 2014; Zheng, 2015), while some argued that there is not significant correlation in it (Cheo & Quah, 2005; Thapa, 2011; Zhang & Liu, 2016; Bray & Lykins, 2012). Whatever, whether or not the private tuition brings to academic achievement to students, the development of the phenomenon is obvious both horizontally and vertically. This highlights to concern more factors beyond academic teaching for a better understanding of the expansion of private tuition. On the other hand, most studies emphasize on students' intention in receiving private tuition and there is little knowledge in the approach from what private tuition provides to the receivers. Bray et al. (2015) suggested that research from different angles is necessary for better understanding of the process of private tuition. Thus, this study aims to explore what the private tuition provides to the receivers beyond what the receivers intense to get in there in order to contribute more theoretical approaches to the study of private tuition.

1.2 Background of the study

Myanmar is a country in Southeast Asia with about 53 million populations within 676,578 km square area. It has about 9.7 million of students and 3.6 lakh of teachers in basic education (MOE, 2017). Basic education consists of primary, middle and high school levels, and the student-teacher ratios are 23:1, 28:1 and 22:1 school respectively. The school system can be said as Kg+4:4:2 form which includes one year of Kindergarten (Kg), 4 years for primary, 4 years for middle and 2 years for high school. The entry age for Kg is 5-year-old and a student can complete basic education at age of 16 if he/she did not repeat any grade. Basic education is totally free for students and the government used more than 6% of the total government expenditure for education in 2015-2016 fiscal years (Thein, 2015; MOE, 2017). Currently, the government is trying to implement Kg+12 education system since 2016-2017 AY. The first semester of the school

calendar starts on 1st June and has about one week of holiday before the second-semester start in October. Generally, the summer holiday is from the end of March to May. The formal school bell generally starts at 9:00 AM and ends in 3:30. The school curriculum emphasizes too much on academic learning while the extracurricular activities represent only 10%-12% of the school curriculum. Each high school class session lasts 45 minutes and there are only 45 minutes in a day for nonacademic works such as moral/civics, vocational/agriculture, physical education/life skill, aesthetic education, and school activity/computer (National Curriculum Review in Myanmar, 2013). Except from Grade 1 and Grade 2, students need to take examinations for each class promotion and only score from core academic subjects are accounted for it. It means the school system does not consider any performance scores from extracurricular activities such as sport, music, and art for any class promotion. Students from Grade 4, Grade 8, and Grade 10 have public examination system for the next level of educational chance. The school incompleteness rate is high at each level of education as 26.2% in the primary, 25.8% in middle school, and 69% in high school respectively (National EFA Review Report, 2014). The school incompleteness rate is dramatic among high school students than others and it would be because of the high stake matriculation examination. Scores from the matriculation examination are the only criterion for higher education admission. The higher scorers likely to get higher prestigious professional tertiary schools. Because of such system, being a high school student is a critical position for a student's life and parents also invest many efforts on it.

Hence, this study focuses on high school students and their experiences on private tuition. Private tuition, as well, has been significantly developing in Myanmar since more than three decades ago. The "Private Academic Teaching Law" enacted by the parliament in 1984 proved the widespread use of private tuition in Myanmar since that time. Gibson (1992) revealed 91% of high school students and 65% of middle school students from Yangon were participating in different forms of private tuition. Although he acknowledged the potential magnitude of private tuition in Myanmar, it lacked to provide the nature of it. As well, little academic literature has known on the process of private tuition in Myanmar.

2. Literature Review

The practice of private tuition has widespread to the nations and its implication to public education and society is significant for both researchers and policymakers. Therefore, Studies need to pay careful attention to the nature and process of private tuition from different angles and contexts from macro, meso or/and micro level(s). This

study focuses on the micro-level process of private tuition in Myanmar and presents a brief discussion on the factors affecting on it.

2.1. Factors Affecting on Private Tuition

As the individual is different, students and parents do not always have the same intention in receiving private tuition. Some of the students would receive private tuition to support their learning while other might receive it because of their environmental influences. Bray (2009) asserted that private tuition primarily evolved to supplement students' works relating to school works but it does not always supportive of students. Sometimes, extreme private tuition can even cause stress to students and can also disturb school functioning.

Nevertheless, the phenomenon developed abundantly and its implications cannot be separated from the mainstream education system. Bray (1999) asserted that private tuition is the product of public education system and its functions are also relating to the school. As well, the deficiency of school structures such as exam-orientation, big class size, and quality of teachers are always the blame on the expanding of private tuition (2009). Many researchers agreed on high stake examination as one of the leading factors in receiving private tuition (Gibson, 1992; Stevenson & Baker, 1992; Bray, 2009; Lee et al., 2010; Zhang & Bray, 2016). They concluded that too much emphasis on competitive structures such as school grading, competitive school admission and reputation both in school and society likely nourish the development of private tuition.

However, there is doubt in asserting factors such as large class size and quality of teachers as the leading factors of private tuition. Bray and Lykins (2012) claimed that many of private tuitions also have large classes and some private tuitions even provide in the huge lecture halls. Of course, some students might receive private tuition because of the formal classes are overcrowded (Tun and Hlaing, 2015), but it would not be the total factor of participating in private tuition. Similarly, private tuitions do not always seem to have better teaching and knowledge skills than school. Bray and Lykins (2012) remarked that parents do not stop of sending their children to private tuition although they knew private tutors cannot improve students' academic performance. On the other hand, people will no longer go to private tuition when they perceive it cannot provide any worthy for them. So, it needs to explore what factors can still keep them in private tuition beyond subject teaching skills.

The above statement highlights students receive private tuition not just because of the quality of the public school is dropped. Some studies concern this concept on parents' and students' doubt on academic learning without private tuition as the

determinants of the expansion of private tuition plus the competitive culture in school enrollment and low quality of public school (Lee et al., 2010). This study figures out the existence of factors such as uncertainty and anxiety for learning among parents and students. Yeah, students probably receive private tuition because of such factors. Bray (2009) asserted private tuition can help increase in students' self-confident for learning, while a study revealed parental concern on the provision private tuition to their children includes to promote students' self-confident for learning (Ireson & Rushforth, 2011). Nonetheless, such findings still need to enrich with how do private tuition help students' self-confident for learning.

In addition, some intentions in receiving private tuition are not for merely academic learning. Those parents provided private tuition without concerning the needs of their children (Lee, 2014) and to have a good relationship with teachers (Kobakhidze, 2014). Zhang (2013) also claimed some parents sent their children to private tuition just because of other parents did it, and some parents have traditional believe as children can develop better under the supervision of their teachers. In this sense, some private tuition provided services such as living and feeding systems in order to welcome students to live under their supervision (Zhang, 2013). This is because some parents provide private tuition for their children not only for subject learning but also for other behavioral guidance.

Students also have different intentions in receiving private tuition. It cannot be generalized all students receive private tuition just for academic performance or to raise their exam scores. Studies revealed that students go to private tuition because their friends are in private tuition (Lee et al., 2010; Zhang, 2013) or as a process of time management skills (Jheng, 2015). As well, some students receive it to have a better relationship with their school teachers (Zhang, 2013). Thus, one cannot hope to see private tuition as only for academic learning and to prepare for the examination. On the other hand, an empirical study is necessary to explore what and how the provisions of private tuitions help to fulfill such different demands from the customers.

In sum, research relating to private tuition in Myanmar context is weak in academic literature even though the phenomenon has been practiced since decades ago. Throughout many worldwide pieces of research on the phenomenon, the blame on the development of private tuition on the poor quality of the public school is still inconclusive. Students seemed to receive private tuition for exam preparation, peer relationship, communication with teachers, and as a competitive culture but a few pieces of research acknowledged how and what private tuitions provide such students' and parental demands. As well, students' participation in private tuition needs more empirical studies through different perspectives and contexts. Therefore, current

research focuses on the magnitude and intensity in receiving private tuition as well as what and how private tuition fulfills such demands.

3. Methodology

3.1. Focus of the Study and Instrument

The study used mixed research design and the instrument was adopted from Bray and Kwo (2015) that has used in Hong Kong context. The general purpose of this study is to investigate what private tuition provides to students beyond what students' intention in receiving it. The study chose Grade 9 students from Kale Township because high school (Grade 9 and Grade 10) is as crucial as the transition edge from high school to tertiary school. Grade 10 students were not selected because of their private study time for the exam. Kale Township was chosen in order to give different context from the previous study on private tuition by Gibson (1992). He just focused on the Southeast part of Myanmar (Yangon Region and Mon State) and this hopes to give better insight on the process of private tuition if the study can provide data from different areas of Myanmar. Kale Township situates on the boundary of Chin State and Sagaing Region in the Northwest part of Myanmar which also has significant diverse cultures within a small township.

The instrument was first adjusted to the local context through experts' suggestions. It excluded concepts such as "tutor king and queen" and "nationality". Then, the questionnaire was translated into Burmese version and sent to two basic school teachers to review whether or not it was clear enough to understand. Throughout feedbacks and suggestions from that two teachers, the instrument was revised and prepared for pilot testing.

3.2 Sampling Design and Data Collection

The study was conducted through the permission of Township Education Office (TEO) and it used purposive sampling design in order to adjust ethnic distribution among the sample. The pilot testing was made with 99 students at one high school in Kale Township which included 76% of Chin ethnic students. It was because Chin ethnic dominated most regions and it needed to ensure whether or not Chin ethnic students had problems in the questionnaire which was in Burmese version. The questionnaire was finalized through lessons from pilot testing and it included 21 items in total.

The study selected 3 rural and 6 urban schools through balancing ethnic distribution. It took more schools from urban areas because urban has more high schools than rural. Besides, one student who receive private tuition and one who do not

receive it in Grade 9 were interviewed from each school. The research encouraged voluntary participation in the study and each participant's personal data was kept in confidentiality. As well, pseudonym systems were used in the report. In total, 1119 students responded the survey questionnaire and 18 students were interviewed from them. Each student spent about 30 minutes to complete the survey questionnaire and the interview took about 15 minutes per one person. The sample involved 53.6% of Chin ethnic students, 45.1% of Burmese ethnic students and 1.3% of the other ethnic groups. Also, 68.5% and 31.5% of the sample represented urban and rural students respectively. The survey data were coded and analyzed with SPSS v23, and the interview data were transcribed and analyzed through Nvivo 10. The data collection and analysis took the total of two months in general

4. Findings

4.1. Scale of private tuition

This study aims to explore the intensity and nature of private tuition in Kale Township. Among the 1119 participants, 971 (88%) students described that they are receiving private tuition in Grade 9 and 1010 (90.3%) students stated they have had experience of it. In addition, 88.5% of Chin students, 87.6% of Burmese students, and 71.5% of others ethnic students are participating in private tuition. As well, 83.4% of rural and 90.1% of urban students in Grade 9 receive private tuition. It means students in urban areas are more likely to participate than rural areas. Following diagram shows students' firstly experienced Grade of receiving private tuition.

Figure 1: First Grade of Receiving Private Tuition

Among students who had experiences of private tuition, 161(15.9%) students started to receive private tuition in their Kindergarten (KG), and 153 of them (95%) still receive private tuition in Grade 9. It shows students who received private tuition since their earlier school-aged time are likely to receive private tuition in high school. As well, 80.6% of Grade 9 students already had experience of private tuition before they are in high school. The number of students who started to receive private tuition increased suddenly when students were at Grade 8. This is because Grade 8 is the transition grade from middle school to high school and it has public examination system. This highlights the number of private tuition receivers increased when there is high stake examination for class promotion. Moreover, the interviewees reported that the reason for increasing students who started to receive Grade 9 includes the intention to prepare for high stake examination in Grade 10. It means even though there is not a public examination in Grade 9, the number of receivers increased in Grade 9 because students perceive Grade 9 as the preparation stage for next Grade 10 examination. As it has been mentioned, exam scores that students will get in matriculation examination or Grade 10 are critical for students' higher education admission. Only students who got highest scores from matriculation examination can get high prestigious professional universities. It makes private tuition receivers increase when their grade level increase.

4.2 Forms of Private Tuition

The study classifies private tuition received by Grade 9 students into five main categories as one to one, small group, large group, boarding tuition and others (see Table 2). The Internet and corresponding tutoring cannot find in this study. It would be because of poor internet connection and poor mailing system. One to one private tuition form means private tuition received by only a student and provided by one or more teacher(s). This kind of private tuition happens in a student's house or the provider(s) home. It can be the teaching of only one subject or all subjects. The local terms this form of private tuition as "guide tuition" because receiving this form of private tuition intense to guide student's learning as a guardian. Therefore, teaching and learning process of one to one private tuition emphasizes on the guidance of student's learning instead of lecturing school curriculum. It can happen both daytime and night. It is a kind of special teaching to only one child and therefore, the fee to receive this form of private tuition is often higher than other forms. Although the provision of one to one private tuition form seems very special for the receivers, the statistics indicates this form of private tuition is the least common form of private tuition among Grade 9 students (Table 2). The reason would be because of the price is high for the normal family to afford it and/or the boredom of receiving private tuition alone.

Table 1: Number and Percentage of Students in Different Forms of Private Tuition

Form of Private Tuition	Frequency	Percentage
One to One	9	.9
Small Group	82	8.4
Large Group	191	19.7
Boarding Tuition	671	69.1
Others	18	1.9
Total	971	100

The second form is small group private tuition. The local termed this form of private tuition as “*wiin* tuition” where “*wiin*” means “round or circle”. It is because this small group private tuition form includes a few students with the teacher(s), and their teaching style is similar to a roundtable discussion among a group of people. As well, this form of private tuition also does not focus on lecturing students excessively. The process can also be private teaching and learning of a subject or all subjects. The form includes both teachings of school lessons and guidance at study time. During these days, there is also “special *wiin* tuition” classified through the price and number of the receivers. “Special *wiin* tuition” receivers are often less than five persons in one group. However, current research mixed them under one content. Among them, only 15 (24.2%) students stated their group includes equal and less than 5 students, 57 (75.8%) students stated about 6 to 25 students in their small groups, and the rests did not provide the number of students in their groups. Generally, the price to receive small group private tuition is cheaper than one to one private tuition form. Thus, the reason of more receivers in this form than one to one private tuition form would be the cheaper in price and/or students can make more friends in there.

The third form of private tuition is the practice of private tuition by a large number of students as in a class or hall. This form of private tuition does not have the limitation of the population for one class and commonly provides all subjects. In addition, this form is the provision of private tuition from school teachers to their own students. As well, private tutors in this form just have a responsibility to provide lectures and do not have guidance session at study time. However, some large private tuition forms, as well, provide guidance in students’ study time. The local termed this form of private tuition as “*Yoeyoe* tuition” where “*Yoeyoe*” means “simple or formal”. Moreover, the price to receive this form of private tuition is not as high as one to one and small group private tuition forms. Besides, this form is the second largest form of private tuition in this study and it would be because of the provision by school teachers and the flexible fee of it.

The fourth form of private tuition is private boarding tuition. This is a common private tuition form in Myanmar and more than two-thirds of private tuition receivers are in it. This private boarding tuition provides all subjects to students. The local termed this form of private tuition as “boarding or *Asuang* tuition” where “*Asuang*” means “hostel, dormitory or boarding system”. It is because this form of private tuition combines both private tuition and boarding systems. Beyond lecture classes and night study, it provides accommodation and feeding system for students. Students who receive private boarding tuition need to live according to the arrangement of that private boarding tuition. Such provision is also very convenient for students who are from other places/regions but seeking to enroll in urban/better schools. This form can help to solve difficulties for students who have challenges for a living and/or transportation to school and can provide extra teaching and guidance in study time. For the teaching and learning, private boarding tuition often has two kinds of private tutors known as teaching tutors and guide tutors. These tutors have different responsibilities.

The teaching tutors have a responsibility to come and teach in the private tuition classes according to the time schedule of the private boarding tuition. The private boarding tuition classes often have large students in one class and their teaching tutors are public school teachers, private professional tutors, and university lecturers. On the other hand, guide tutors are often university students and people who graduated from high school or university. Guide tutors have responsibility to look whether or not students pay close attention to the lecturing by the teaching tutors in private tuition classes, to take care when students go to school and to bring back all of them together after school, to guide and explain students' homework and learning at study time, to restrict each student to follow the boarding tuition's disciplines, and to do other works relating to the students and boarding tuition. Sometimes, guide tutors are as agents to meet students' parents for students' needs; as advertisers to recruit students through making advertisements such as poster sticking on the billboards or public areas, making pamphlet distribution, and as servants to do miscellaneous things relating to the private tuition. Through the provision of services as teaching, accommodation, and guidance at study time, the price to receive private boarding is nearly the same with one to one private tuition forms. However, it can provide more services than another form of private tuitions and this would be the reason of why most students receive it.

The final category of private tuition in this study includes two different cases. The first case is the practice of any form of private tuition classes at day time and then the hiring of a guide tutor for night study. Only one student reports such practice throughout this study. She reported as she goes to private boarding tuition classes at day time and then she purchases a guide tutor for her night study. The price to receive

such system is high because it is similar to the practice of two private tuition forms by only one person. Thus, it seems only a few students can do it. The second case is the provision of private boarding tuition by monasteries or social organizations. Their aim is not to make a profit through providing private tuition but to help students and families who have limitations to receive private tuition. Many university teachers, public basic school teachers, and other private tutors are volunteering in such private tuition. Sometimes, the monastic monks in that monastery provide lecture classes if they can. However, such private tuitions are not free for all students who want to receive it. Only those students who have special cases (e.g. orphan) and financial difficulties can access such private tuition with free of charge or only a limited amount of money. Besides, every student who wants to receive such private tuition needs to pass placement test by the private tuition. Because of such limitations, students who receive this form of private tuition are not common although the cost is not high.

In general, private boarding tuition is the most common form of private tuition among Grade 9 students in Kale Township. It is popular because of its provision of living and learning conditions. As well, the price is reasonable for students and parents. In contrast, one to one private tuition form is the least common form in this study. Although there are different in private tuition forms, all private tuition forms seem to provide not only teaching of school lessons to the students but also guidance in students learning and study time.

4.3 Providers of Private Tuition

The study continues exploring of private tutors in different private tuition forms. According to the survey (see Table 3), not less than half (53.5%) of the private tutors are public school teachers. It shows school teachers are the main providers of private tuition and then, professional private tutors are the second main providers of it. Private tuition providing by university students and teachers is not so significant as in this study. This would be because of university teachers also have private tuition to their students and university students better serve as guide tutors in private boarding tuition instead of private teaching tutors. Sometimes, monastic monks also teach school subjects to students if the private tuition is under their control.

Table 2: Providers of Private Tuition

Type of Tutors	Frequency	Valid Percent (%)
Students' own teachers in school	347	37.3
Other teachers from the same school	118	12.7
Teachers from another school	33	3.5
Professional private tutors	75	8.1
Both the combination of private tutors and school teachers	337	36.2
Included university students and/or lecturers	20	2.1
Others	1	0.1
Missing	40 (4.1%)	

4.4 Reasons for Receiving Private Tuition

Students were asked to describe their intention of participating in private tuition through some given lists and space options for more reasons. Generally, more than half (60%) of students described that they participate in private tuition in order to learn subjects more. This means students are not totally satisfying with the school teaching, and they seek more teaching and knowledge skills in private tuition. Afterward, hoping to get high exam scores ranks the second common reason for participating in private tuition. According to figure 2, students who receive private tuition because of their parental desires are more than students who receive it because of peer pressure and advertisements by private tuition. Besides, some students described their intention in receiving private tuition as the preparation courses for matriculation examination; to control their laziness for learning; a culture of practice; a supplementary course because of hard to catch up with classmates, because of teachers do not teach well in school and big class size; to be ahead than others; a supporter to get their big dream; and a place which has specific time management skills. In short, receiving private tuition includes two main reasons as to have a supporter for their learning, and to receive it without having any personal intention. Yeah, some students receive it with any expectation in there but some receive it as a habit.

Figure 2: Main Reasons of Receiving Private Tuition

4.5 What do Private Tuition Provide to Students?

Beyond students' intention in receiving private tuition, the study explored what students do get in there through interviewing 18 students. The interviewees were coded as N1, N2, N3,, N9 for students who did not receive private tuition in Grade 9 and T1, T2, T3,, T9 for students who received it. Among them, only N2 and N6 never had any experience of private tuition in their studies while only T8 and T9 started to receive it in Grade 9. It means 88.9% of the interviewees have had experiences of private tuition and 77.8% of them already had experiences of private tuition before they were high school students. Besides, 5 students (T3, T4, T5, T6, and T7) in the interviewees who received private tuition were from different areas of their current schools. They came to study in urban/more developed areas from their villages/areas through receiving private boarding tuition. This shows many students in urban schools are not from the urban residence and it makes students more in urban than rural areas.

Even though the quantitative data described students' intentions in receiving private tuition are to get more subjects knowledge and teaching skills, interviewed students reported that there are not significant differences in teaching and knowledge skills among school and private tuition. For this sense, some students remarked their opinion on students' academic achievements as *"No, school achievement is because of the result of hard working. It is not the result of private tuition"* (N6), and *"There are many students who receive private tuition but poor in school performance. So, it depends on personal hard working skill; not on private tuition"* (N8). As well, many students perceived that there are not differences in the provision of teaching and knowledge skills among school and private tuition. They expressed their experiences as: *"It is not different from*

school and private tuition teaching. We learn again what we learned in school” (N9), “No, private tuition and school have the same teachers. It is the same in teaching both in school and private tuition” (T1), and “I think it is the same (teaching skills between school and private tuition)” (T3). Of course, it might be true because most tutors in private tuitions are also from school teachers and it is reasonable to claim the school and private tuition do not have a significant difference in teaching and knowledge skills. In addition, public school teachers would probably have better teaching skills than private professional tutors because they have more theoretical and practical training in teaching than many professional private tutors. Hence, even private tuition provides teaching to students, it seems private tuition cannot provide better teaching and knowledge skills than school.

If there are not differences in teaching and knowledge skills among school and private tuition, it needs to explore more on the process of private tuition which makes students participate in it. In general, the private teaching processes happen before and after the school hours. Students need to get up at 5:00 AM and need to study till 10:30 PM. They have two sessions of lecture classes before they go to public school at 9:00 AM and have at least two lecture classes again after school. Students "T2" explains his experience as *"we need to wake up at 4:30 AM and study from 5:00 AM to 6:00 AM. Then, we start lecture classes as 6:00 AM to 7:30 AM for one session and 7:00 AM to 8:25 AM for one session. Afterward, we have breakfast and go to school. The school ends at 3:30 PM and we have two private tuition classes as from 4:00 PM to 5:00 PM, and from 5:00 PM to 6:00 PM. Then, we have dinner and, start night study at 7:00 PM. We go to bed at 10:00 PM"* (T7). This is the common process of private tuition except in large group private tuition. There are just some differences in time duration per class, time to wake up and go to bed. Some private tuitions make students get up at 5:00 AM and go to bed at 11:00 PM, and some of them have lecture classes that take more than 1 hour. In private boarding tuition, guide tutors are always with students at lecture classes and study time. Even though one to one and small group private tuition do not have guide tutors, their private tutors serve as both teaching and guide tutors. As well, some large group tuitions do not focus on teaching and they emphasize on learning and making exercises with private tutors. Most teachers in large group tuition are exactly the same teachers from schools for students, and they just have revision exercises and explanation again some concepts from school lessons. It means students whomever in private tuition do not merely get teaching and knowledge skills of their private tutors but also guidance in their learning and study time. While the school can provide just subject teachings within their school hours, private tuition can provide both teachings and other services such as guidance in study time. In general, the school has just 7 hours a day with students while almost the rest of the time is under the control of private tuition.

However, students did not seem to totally satisfied with the teaching and knowledge skills of private tuition. For instance, a student remarks her private tutors as *"They are not so helpful in private tuition. They leave the class as soon as they finished their sessions"* (T5). Student "T5" is a student who receives private boarding tuition and she remarks the unreliable of their teaching tutors for their learning in private tuition. This shows teaching tutors in private boarding tuitions are not really students' happiness of receiving it although more than two-third of private tuition receivers are in there. In another word, about 70% of private tuition receivers in this study remain in private tuition not because of they are totally satisfying in the teaching and knowledge provided by private tuition. The teaching tutors in private boarding tuition just come and teach in their time, and leave the class as soon as they finished their sessions. So, students rarely have time to discuss and learn about problems they encountered in their learning with their teaching tutors. Therefore, it can conclude that even students claimed they want to get more subjects skills and knowledge, it would be a debatable question on whether or not private tuition can really provide better subject teaching skills than school.

Indeed, what the private tuition provides to students and why students are satisfying in it need to explore beyond mere teaching and knowledge skills by the private tutors. It is necessary if private tuition and school do not have significant teaching skills, and private teaching tutors are not also helpful for students in private tuition. Thus, the study tried to explore more factors which keep students in private tuition in addition to the teaching of lessons. This is because no one will continue to receive private tuition if they cannot find something worthy of them. In this sense, the study found some interrelated factors such as some people cannot learn in their homes because their neighbors are quarreling, their siblings are playing, their parents are talking loudly, there is no one who can help them in their learning difficulties, and/or many reasons. Yeah, many parents also do not have knowledge background and time to look their children's learning. For instance, student "N3" claimed as *"my parents are very busy and do not have any knowledge to guide my study. So, they sent me to private tuition"* (N3). Perhaps, some students are lazy and do not turn on books if they do not have someone to enforce them. From many of such conditions, students need a learning environment and parents also seek for it. It can be seen in the interviews as *"receiving private tuition is good. We need to learn and study although we don't want to do it"* (N9), and *"my most favorite system in private tuition is their specific timetable of to eat, learn, study and sleep"* (N6). These highlights factors which attach students in private tuition include the services such as discipline guidelines, specific timetable, and guidance in their learning difficulties. Of course, the living and feeding system in private boarding system are

already good services for students from rural/remote or different areas, the provision of lecturing and specific disciplines in private tuition will enrich students' learning. Such provisions are favorable not only for rural/remote students to come and receive private tuition in order to enroll in urban/better schools but also for children who have challenges to study at home alone.

Moreover, it seems such provisions might be the factor in the likelihood of high achievement by private tuition receivers. In spite of mere teaching in the classroom, many students described their guide tutors' help for their learning improvement. One student expressed his/her learning situation as *"Guide tutors are hovering around us to look whether or not we concentrate on the teaching. So, we pay closer attention in private tuition classes' teachings"* (T3). This short speech mentions about the role of guide tutors in private boarding tuition and highlights their learning improvement because of them. Similarly, students replied the question of to whom they often go for help in their learning difficulties as *"I mostly go for help to my guide tutors"* (T5), and *"my guide tutors give more help because they are always with us"* (T4). These interviewed notes reveal the importance of guide tutors in private tuition as resource persons for their learning. Such provision in private boarding tuition is adorable for a learning environment. Even though lecture classes in private boarding tuitions are also crowded, they often have guide tutors to support students' individual learning. For instance, there are 22 guide tutors for 193 students in a private tuition received by student "T4". She said as *"in our private tuition, one guide tutor has responsible on 6 students' learning and even they can't explain our exercises, they guide us to people who can explain it"* (T4). This is a great provision of student-teacher ratio that public school can hardly do it. Other private boarding tuitions also have a similar provision. For instance, private boarding tuition received by student "T7" has 2 guide tutors for 40 students and "T3" has 3 guide tutors for 59 students. It shows private boarding tuition can provide about 1 guide tutor for 20 students. On the other hand, even for the national level in public school, the student-teacher ratio is about 22:1 in high school and most of the sampled schools have 40 to more than 80 students in one class. This means private tuition can provide better personal guidance or face to face teaching to students. Thus, the private tuition seems to have a better supportive learning environment for teaching and learning than school. In addition, a significant ratio of this survey reported that students received private tuition because the school classes were big and they cannot learn effectively.

Yeah, there were already small amount of students with the teacher(s) in one to one and small group private tuition forms, they would no longer need guide tutors for their learning. Also, their teaching tutors already served them as guide tutors even in their night study time. Moreover, student "T8" described his large group private tuition

form as *"we don't have lectures. Our tutors said we will not listen well in school teaching if we have lectures in private tuition. Only if we have some specific problems in doing exercises, we use Blackboard for explaining it. In other time, we do our homework and study, and the tutors look for whether or not we get it"* (T8). It means all of these – one to one, small group and large private tuition forms – have some kind of services in students' learning than mere teaching of school lessons or they emphasized on guiding of students' learning instead of preaching school lessons through Blackboard.

Therefore, it can conclude that students do not get just mere teaching and knowledge skills from their private tuitions. Even private tuition seems incapable of providing more subjects and teaching skills than school, it seems to have better services for students' learning environment. It is also unreasonable if someone claimed private tuition can provide better subject and knowledge skills than public school. However, private tuition likely to have better supportive environment such as specific timetable, living condition, feeding system and guidance for learning difficulties than public school and home can do. On the other hand, as the urbanization process, people often seeks for better welfares, living and other social services since the early human being. People moves and seeks for a place where more and better resources are easily available for them. They believe that such factors are necessary for their personal development and future life. Thus, they invest their efforts such as money and time in it. As well, parents and students conceive services provided in private tuition such as teaching, guidance, specific rules and other supports are necessary for learning and for preparing for future life.

5. Limitation and Recommendation for further study

First of all, although this research aimed to give insight from what the private tuition provides to students instead of what students' intention in it, the study cannot observe and interview the private tuition centers and providers. However, it should not mean this study is totally from the wrong approach because students are the participators in private tuition and their experiences are also worth than what the private tuition pretend to provide to students. As well, this research is just the reflections of Grade 9 students in Kale Township and all data are from their perspectives. Hence, it needs to be aware of too much generalization in interpreting the data. Nonetheless, the findings from this study can apply in similar contexts within in Myanmar. Also, the different forms of private tuition and their characteristics in this research can apply to ground theory for other research on private tuition in Myanmar. Further studies are strongly recommended to explore more data through different perspectives and it can use

current findings as a theoretical contribution in research on the provision of private tuition within Myanmar and other countries. Such broad scene finding will better support policy implementation for the development of private tuition and its impacts on the public education system.

6. Conclusion

The development of private tuition has been significant not only in Kale Township and Myanmar but also around nations. The study tried to explore what the private tuition provides to students beyond the scale and intentions in receiving it. Through the survey and interview, it can generalize that more than 90% of high school students have had experiences of different forms of private tuition and about 80% already participated in private tuition before there were in high school. Besides, 88% of Grade 9 students receive private tuition in this study while Gibson (1992) reported 91% of high school students in Yangon (Rangoon) Region were in private tuition. Despite the time variation among these two studies, it seems about 90% of high school students in Myanmar receive private tuition. However, it needs to explore in the broader contexts to talk about the nation as a whole though Myanmar is so diverse both in geographical, ethnical and religious natures.

Private tuition forms vary from country to country and/or region to region as: one to one, small group, large group or private tuition provided by school teachers, private tutors, university students and lecturers, business groups, correspondence courses, broadcasting system, and internet tutoring (Bray, 2009; Bray & Lykins, 2012; Lee et al., 2010; Zhang & Liu, 2016). As well, Myanmar seems to have a common private tuition form called private boarding tuition that is rare to see in another context. Besides, it is the most common form among the participants and more than two-thirds of private tuition receivers in this study are in private boarding tuition. The private boarding tuition has two kinds of private tutors known as guide tutors and teaching tutors. All private tuition forms in this study similarly provide guiding in students' learning or study beyond the mere teaching of school lessons through the board.

In general, students showed strong expectation to learn subjects more in private tuition but many students reported there is not a difference in teaching between private tuition and school. As the school classrooms are crowded, many boarding tuition classes are also crowded and many of their teachers are not so helpful for their face to face learning and discussion both in private tuition and school. In addition, more than half of private tutors are from public schools, and students remarked that private tuition does not have significant subject teaching skills than school. On the other hand,

students highlighted their preferences on a specific timetable, reinforcement, and guidance in private tuition. This would link to the new institutional perspective on educational development while Davies, Quirke, and Aurini (2006) argued that the new development of educational institution (e.g. private tuition) can better provide face to face conversation, personal guidance and more suitable environment for individual's learning. Stevenson and Baker (1992) also posited that the intention of investing money in private tuition includes having a better place for students where learning resources (e.g. teaching, guidance, reinforcement) are easily available. Therefore, it can conclude that students and parents are buying environmental services for learning in private tuition in addition to the teaching of school subjects. As well, policymakers in education need to concern such environmental needs for students' learning for better public service in the further education system.

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